

Effect of Microbial Consortium and Organic Stimulant on Maize Growth in Bitumen-Polluted Soil

Adeniyi, A. A.^{1*}, Oyedeji, O.³, Adeyemo, S. M.³, Awotoye, O. O.²

1 - Department of Environmental Management and Toxicology, University of Ilesa, Ilesa, Osun State

2 - Institute of Ecology and Environmental Studies, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

3 - Department of Microbiology, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

Abstract

This study evaluated the growth rate of maize (*Zea mays*) in bitumen-polluted soil and assessed the effectiveness of bioremediation treatments in supporting its growth. The bitumen sample was collected from Agbabu, Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State, and unpolluted soil was collected from a control area. The raw bitumen was mixed with the soil using standard methods. A consortium of previously identified hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria, along with a treatment incorporating fish pond waste (FPW) as an organic stimulant, was introduced into the polluted soil. A greenhouse experiment was conducted with five treatments, each replicated three times, for a total of fifteen experimental units. Each treatment consisted of 5 kg of sieved soil in a plastic pot, and three maize seeds were sown per pot, later thinned to one plant per pot two weeks after sowing. Growth parameters (number of leaves, plant height, leaf length, leaf width, and leaf area) were measured biweekly from the third week until harvest. The results showed varying responses across the different treatments. The bitumen-polluted soil treated with the bacterial consortium and biostimulant (FPW) improved leaf area and plant height over 10 weeks. A notable improvement in plant height was observed when the bacterial isolates were biostimulated with FPW. Leaf width was consistently enhanced by both the bacterial consortium alone and the consortium combined with the organic stimulant throughout the growth period. This study concluded that both the bacterial consortium and organic amendment (fish pond waste) had a positive impact on the growth performance of maize in bitumen-polluted soil.

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1. Introduction

Contaminated soil with petroleum products, such as bitumen, has increasingly become a global environmental concern. This type of pollution endangers the health of the soil due to reduced fertility and its capacity to serve agricultural production (Adipah, 2019; Ossai et al., 2020). The following changes may occur when bitumen contaminates the soil: reduced airflow, nutrients become unavailable and lessened microbial activities (Asubiojo and Adebisi, 2011; Atojunere, 2021; Jekayinfa et al., 2023). Such changes make it difficult for plant growth and development and for staple crops, like maize (*Zea mays* L.), which represent one of the most important human foodstuffs, animal feed, and raw materials for many industries across the globe.

Maize is a sensitive cereal crop and thus serves as a leading indicator of soil quality and fertility. The hydrophobic nature of hydrocarbons modifies the rate of water infiltration and root penetration in bitumen-contaminated soils, while their toxicity inhibits germination of seeds and affects plant growth (Sithole et al., 2016; Li et al., 2019; Suganya et al., 2020; Hu et al., 2021; Shah et al., 2023). Thus, remediation processes are vital to restore the quality of soil and sustain crop production in such environments.

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*Corresponding author

Email address: adetomiadeniyi@gmail.com, adetomi_adeniyi@unilesa.edu.ng

Bioremediation has been introduced as an environmentally-friendly and cost-effective remedy for soil pollution. This may involve the use of microbial consortia, or a group of microorganisms and have been reported to yield promising results. The microbial consortium works on the hydrocarbons to perform their toxic actions through diverse pathways of action on degradation to change toxic compounds into less harmful substances. These microorganisms also bear the additional capacity to improve soil structure and nutrient cycling, thereby creating a better ambience for plants to grow in (Zhang, 2010; Ahmad, 2022; Lázaro-Mass, 2023).

Additionally, microbial consortia work more effectively with the application of organic stimulants, such as fish pond waste, to promote soil remediation. Organic stimulants restore important nutrients to the soil, boost microbial activity, and enhance hydrocarbon degradations (Patil, 2021; Aditya, 2022; Sirohi, 2022). Fish pond waste, in particular, is rich in nitrogen, phosphorus, and organic carbon, all of which are essential for plant growth and microbial growth. The combined inoculation of microbial consortia and organic stimulants is a promising method for the restoration of bitumen-contaminated soils and the growth of maize under such conditions (Mustapha and El Bakali, 2021; Bai et al., 2023; Luo, 2023).

The aim of this study was to assess the joint effects of a microbial consortium and an organic stimulant, fish pond waste, on the growth performance of maize in bitumen-polluted soils. The study evaluates the remediation potential of these treatments, as well as the effect on soil quality and maize productivity, to offer insights into sustainable agricultural practices in polluted environments.

2. Materials and Method

2.1. Study Area

Soil (contaminated) samples for the study were obtained from Agbabu, Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria (Figure 1). It lies within geographical coordinates latitude 6° 35' 16.3"N and 6° 37' 13.9"N and longitudes 4° 49' 29.0"E and 4° 50' 20.7"E. Agbabu is one of the major towns located in the Nigerian natural bitumen belt and the place where bitumen was first discovered in Nigeria in 1910 and the first bitumen well NBC-7 was drilled there. Agbabu field is part of the vast deposits of heavy oil and natural bitumen in the Dahomey Basin. The Dahomey basin is a coastal sedimentary basin that spans from Ghana-Ivory Coast border to western Nigeria (Mosobalaje et al., 2019). The presence of heavy oil and natural bitumen deposits in the eastern part of the Dahomey basin has been affirmed by several authors (MSMD, 2006; Akinmosin et al., 2012; Adeyemi et al., 2013).

The Agbabu bitumen belt is made of the main Agbabu village comprising about 400 people and other smaller farm settlements such as Temidire village made up of about 200 people. Farmers in this area deal mainly in cash crops such as cocoa, colanut, food crops such as yam, maize, plantain and fishing along River Oluwa which flows through the whole land. These villages depend on River Oluwa for their farming activities and other domestic use. Bitumen sample was collected from the well located at the back of the King of Agbabu's Palace.

2.2. Sample Collection

Bitumen sample was collected from Agbabu in Ondo State. Soil was collected from an area with minimal anthropogenic activity to exclude pollution for the greenhouse experiment.

2.2.1. Soil Samples

Undisturbed soil samples were collected randomly at depth of 0-15 cm. Samples were appropriately labelled and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

2.2.2. Bitumen collection

The bitumen sample was collected from the bitumen well behind the King of Agbabu's Palace via a container lowered into the well. Adequate quantity (5 litres) was collected to ensure sufficient amount of the same sample was used for microbial and chemical analysis. Samples for microbiological analysis were collected inside sterile McCartney bottles.

2.3. Fish Pond Waste

Fish Pond Waste (FPW) was the organic amendment used for this study. The FPW was collected from a Fish Pond Farm at Parakin, Ile-Ife, Osun State. The sample was air dried, crushed and then passed through a 0.5 mm mesh sieve and used as biostimulant. The organic amendment (FPW) was used as substrate to stimulate microbial growth and boost their metabolism.

2.3.1. Addition of Fish Pond Waste to Soil Sample

As described by Ugboma et al. (2020), the amendment (fish pond waste) was dried and filtered using a 0.5 mm mesh sieve (Amechi et al., 2016). Appropriate masses of air-dried soil were amended with the fish pond waste (FPW) at the rate of 10 g/kg.

2.4. Screenhouse Degradation Experiment

The objective of the Screenhouse soil culture experiment was to assess the effect of microbial petroleum hydrocarbon remediation on maize (*Zea mays* L.) growth and nutrients uptake by maize in both the soil and amended samples. The soil sample (loam soil) for planting was obtained from the Parks and Garden Unit of the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. The soil obtained was air-dried and then sieved with a 2 mm mesh sieve.

2.4.1. Contamination of soil

The soil to be used was autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min to expel influence of unwanted microbial life before use, to ensure the availability and utilization of the microorganisms introduced into the contaminated soil (Soretire et al., 2017). Bitumen obtained from Agbabu was used to contaminate the soil for planting. The soil was contaminated with 1.5 % of the bitumen (contaminant). Five kilogram portions of air-dried soil was weighed and put on polyethene sheet. Seventy five grams of bitumen was weighed and added to the soil and mixed thoroughly by hand. It was then left for two weeks for the contaminant to properly mix and settle into the soil.

2.4.2. Biostimulant application

Fish pond waste (FPW) was added to the contaminated soil in the pot at the rate of 10 g/kg. Fifty gram of the FPW was added to the soil portions and then thoroughly mixed by hand. The soil samples and treatments, in triplicates were returned into plastic pots perforated (about 2 cm) at the bottom to allow for free flow of air.

2.4.3. Inoculation of the isolated organisms to the polluted soil in the screenhouse

Five organisms with optimal bitumen-degrading performance were previously isolated from bitumen polluted soil and were identified as *Brevundimonas naejangsanensis*, *Chryseobacterium gleum*, *Enterobacter tabaci*, *Salmonella enterica* and *Chryseobacterium flavum*. These were used for the microbial synergistic combination for this study.

The microbial consortiums were previously screened and the consortium with optimal performance used. The modified method of Arinze et al. (2022) was adapted for this study. Three hundred millilitres of cultured microbes in peptone water were added to the pretreated soil portions (previously autoclaved soil). This was thoroughly mixed and left for a week for the microorganisms to acclimatize and adapt well in the soil before planting. Three maize (*Zea mays* L) seeds were planted per pot.

2.4.4. Bioremediation treatment design

The maize seeds were planted using the contaminated soil (with bitumen) with varying treatment. Four microorganisms were used for this purpose in a synergistic relationship. The experimental set-up consisted of five treatment plans and is shown in Table 1.

The Completely Randomized Design (CRD) was used as the experimental design and replicated three times. The soil was thoroughly tilled to mix nutrients with the polluted soil, enhance aeration and microbial metabolism. The experiments were carried out in triplicates.

2.4.5. Maize Seeds

Maize seeds of the appropriate qualities were collected from the Department of Crop Production and Protection, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, for the purpose of this study. The seeds were of the variety 2014-TZE-YDT-STR.variables.

2.4.6. Sowing

Five kilograms of soil was weighed into each planting pot and replicated thrice for each treatment. Three seedlings of maize were planted per pot. After germination, the seedlings were thinned to one per pot after two weeks. The pots were watered to about 75 % water holding capacity every other day. The experiment was run for 10 weeks. Growth indicating parameters such as plant height, number of leaf per plant, leaf area per plant were measured. Plant height (cm) was measured from the base of the plant to upper part; the top most leaves. The total number of functional leaves of each plant was measured by a visual count of the green leaves. The leaf area was calculated as the product of leaf length and widest middle portion of the leaf and multiplied by correction factor 0.75 (Rajeshwari *et al.*, 2007; Berdjour *et al.*, 2020).

$$\text{Leaf Area} = \text{Leaf length} \times \text{Leaf width} \times 0.75 \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

After the measurements of the growth parameters, the plants with their roots were harvested and dried. A 5 g sub sample of soil was taken from each pot for further analysis (Antonious and Snyder, 2007).

Table 1: Experimental Treatments in the Screenhouse for Bioremediation

S/N	Soil	Treatment
1	Contaminated soil (5kg)	Organisms
2	Contaminated soil (5kg)	Organisms + FPW (50 g)
3	Contaminated soil (5kg)	FPW (50 g)
4	Contaminated soil (5kg)	-
5	Uncontaminated (5 kg)	(Control)

2.4.7. Tissue Analysis

Tissues were milled in a Wiley Micro-hammer Stainless Steel Mill and passed through a 40-mesh sieve prior to chemical analysis. After being placed in clean aluminum foil bags, the maize tissues were taken to the laboratory and split into shoot and root. All the tissues were washed with deionized water, air dried, pulverized to pass through a 40-mesh sieve, and finally stored at -20°C until analysis.

2.5. Extraction of Petroleum Hydrocarbons

2.5.1 Extraction of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons in Soil

Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons in the soil was extracted using a Soxhlet extractor according to the method described by Association of Official Analytical Chemists, (AOAC, 2005). Five grams of each sample was weighed and 5 g of anhydrous sodium sulphate added to each sample and thoroughly mixed. The samples were placed in Cellulose thimble and extracted for 6 hours using 150 mL of dichloromethane in a soxhlet apparatus. The extracts were concentrated by

evaporation overnight in a fume cupboard while covering with a perforated aluminum foil. Samples were analyzed before and after the bioremediation process.

2.5.2. Sample clean - up of the TPH extract

This was carried out according to the method described by Alinnor and Nwachukwu, (2013). Sample clean-up was performed using a glass column. Column preparation was carried out by inserting glass wool into the column. Silica gel (silica gel was activated in an oven by heating at 103 °C for 4 h) was dissolved with dichloromethane (DCM) to form slurry, and the slurry added into the column. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was added into the column and eluted by the addition of n-hexane. After preparing the column, the concentrated sample extract was loaded onto the prepared column and eluted with 50 mL n-hexane. The eluent was collected into a beaker below the column. The eluted sample was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature in a fume cupboard for evaporation to take place. A known volume (1.0 mL) of the extract was transferred into a well labeled vial and stored at 4 °C prior to Gas Chromatographic Flame Ionization Detector (GC-FID) analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Screenhouse Experiment

The growth performance of maize plant under the influence of bacterial isolates and biostimulants in a bitumen polluted soil are presented in Tables 2 - 6. The number of leaves of maize varied across treatments and weeks. The bacterial isolates did not enhance the number of leaves in the treatment with bitumen-contaminated soil. However, under the influence of a biostimulant, the bacteria isolates improved the number of leaves across the growth period. The influence of biostimulant only on bitumen contaminated soil showed appreciable increase in the number of leaves compared to the other treatments (contaminated soil + bacterial isolates and contaminated soil + bacterial isolates + biostimulant). Incidentally, the untreated bitumen contaminated soil had higher number of leaves (17) towards the end of the experiment compared to other treatments (Table 2).

The pattern of plant height of maize grown in bitumen contaminated soil under different treatments were similar to that of number of leaves from ages two (2) to six (6) weeks after planting (Table 4.6). At eight and ten weeks after sowing, application of biostimulant only significantly enhanced the plant height of maize compared to other treatments in a bitumen contaminated soil. Introduction of bacterial isolates only did not show any positive influence on the plant height of maize in bitumen contaminated soil. However, when the bacterial isolates were biostimulated (with FPW), there was an appreciable improvement in the plant height of maize. Similar to the number of leaves, the plant height of maize was not inhibited in bitumen contaminated soil (Table 2).

The leaf length of maize in bitumen contaminated soil under the influence of bacteria isolates and biostimulants followed the same trend with the plant heights (Table 3). The leaf lengths under the influence of bacterial isolates were significantly lower than other treatments (Table 3). In contrast to leaf length, the leaf width of maize plant was enhanced by both bacterial isolates only and bacterial isolates augmented with biostimulant throughout the period of growth. Untreated bitumen contaminated soil had the lowest leaf width (Table 4).

The leaf area of maize plants grown on bitumen contaminated soil treated with bacterial isolates was not different from untreated contaminated soil (Table 5). However, when the bacterial isolates were aided with biostimulant in bitumen contaminated soil, the leaf area was significantly improved compared to the unaided bacterial isolates. Bitumen contaminated soil had the highest leaf area compared to other treatments.

The TPH concentrations across various parameters derived from maize tissues planted under different treatments and post-crop soil using bitumen-contaminated soil (BCS) are presented in Table 7. The initial total petroleum hydrocarbon concentration of the soil for each treatment was 68.31 ± 0.02 mg/kg. After harvesting, the level of hydrocarbon content in the soil (post-crop soil) varied with each treatment. The least was observed in the treatment with microorganisms and fish pond waste (CSOE, 10.28 ± 0.04 mg/kg) while the highest was from contaminated soil only (CS, 15.17 ± 0.00 mg/kg) (Table 5). The plant root from the contaminated soil only had a TPH concentration of 4.27 ± 0.04 mg/kg. This was the highest concentration of TPH from the plant root of all treatments while the least was from contaminated soil with microorganisms (0.35 ± 0.00 mg/kg). This implies the presence of microorganisms in the roots resulted in a lower TPH concentration and also accumulation in the root compared to the treatment without microorganism

Table 2: Number of Leaves of Maize Plants as Influenced by Bacterial Isolates under Bitumen Contaminated Soil

Treatments	Number of Weeks				
	2	4	6	8	10
Contaminated soil + Bacterial Isolates	4.00 ^c ±0.58	5.00 ^c ±0.58	7.00 ^c ±0.58	10.00 ^c ±0.0	12.00 ^d ±0.58
Contaminated soil + Bacterial Isolates + Biostimulant	5.00 ^b ±0.01	7.00 ^b ±0.58	9.00 ^b ±0.00	11.00 ^b ±0.00	13.00 ^c ±0.58
Contaminated soil + Biostimulant	6.00 ^a ±0.58	8.00 ^a ±0.58	10.00 ^a ±0.00	13.00 ^a ±0.58	15.00 ^b ±0.58
Contaminated soil	4.00 ^c ±0.58	7.00 ^b ±0.58	10.00 ^a ±0.58	13.00 ^a ±0.50	17.00 ^a ±0.50
Control soil	4.00 ^c ±0.00	6.00 ^c ±0.05	8.00 ^c ±0.01	9.00 ^d ±0.00	11.00 ^e ±0.00

* Mean with different superscripts within the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$); Bacterial Isolates - A1D3E1Z2

Table 3: Plant Height (cm) of Maize Plants as influenced by Bacterial Isolates under Bitumen Contaminated Soil

Treatments	Number of Weeks				
	2	4	6	8	10
Contaminated soil + Bacteria Isolates	15.30 ^d ±0.20	24.70 ^b ±0.20	32.17 ^e ±0.12	41.57 ^e ±0.06	50.37 ^e ±0.15
Contaminated soil + Bacterial Isolates + Biostimulant	21.70 ^c ±0.20	33.67 ^b ±0.12	45.30 ^d ±0.10	53.50 ^d ±0.10	60.27 ^d ±0.15
Contaminated soil + Biostimulant	22.70 ^b ±0.20	35.60 ^a ±0.20	52.15 ^b ±0.15	61.37 ^a ±0.15	69.10 ^a ±0.26
Contaminated soil	21.33 ^c ±0.31	32.77 ^b ±0.25	53.10 ^a ±0.30	59.17 ^b ±0.35	65.70 ^b ±0.20
Control soil	23.27 ^a ±0.15	31.70 ^b ±0.20	48.60 ^c ±0.10	56.63 ^c ±0.12	62.40 ^c ±0.10

* Mean with different superscripts within the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$); Bacterial Isolates - A1D3E1Z2

Table 4: Leaf Length (cm) of Maize Plants as influenced by Bacterial Isolates under Bitumen Contaminated Soil

Treatments	Number of Weeks				
	2	4	6	8	10
Contaminated soil + Bacteria Isolates	5.90 ^d ±0.10	11.50 ^c ±0.10	21.37 ^d ±0.15	30.80 ^e ±0.20	37.60 ^e ±0.15
Contaminated soil + Bacterial Isolates + Biostimulant	6.50 ^c ±0.10	12.50 ^b ±0.20	23.70 ^c ±0.20	32.17 ^d ±0.12	40.63 ^d ±0.15
Contaminated soil + Biostimulant	9.37 ^a ±0.15	14.30 ^a ±0.02	25.80 ^a ±0.20	36.37 ^a ±0.15	48.43 ^a ±0.12
Contaminated soil	8.70 ^b ±0.20	12.17 ^b ±0.31	23.90 ^c ±0.20	35.30 ^b ±0.17	43.80 ^b ±0.20
Control soil	6.37 ^c ±0.15	12.37 ^b ±0.15	24.87 ^b ±0.12	33.13 ^c ±0.15	42.67 ^c ±0.12

* Mean with different superscripts within the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$); Bacterial Isolates - A1D3E1Z2

Table 5: Leaf Width (cm) Of Maize Plants As influenced By Bacteria Isolates under Bitumen Contaminated Soil

Treatments	Number of Weeks				
	2	4	6	8	10
Contaminated soil + Bacteria Isolates	3.10 ^c ±0.10	4.53 ^b ±0.15	6.23 ^c ±0.15	7.87 ^b ±0.15	9.07 ^b ±0.15
Contaminated soil + Bacterial Isolates + Biostimulant	3.37 ^b ±0.15	4.67 ^b ±0.15	6.50 ^b ±0.10	8.17 ^a ±0.15	9.40 ^a ±0.15
Contaminated soil + Biostimulant	3.27 ^{bc} ±0.15	4.50 ^b ±0.10	5.73 ^d ±0.15	6.93 ^c ±0.15	8.07 ^c ±0.15
Contaminated soil	3.09 ^c ±0.15	4.23 ^c ±0.15	5.47 ^e ±0.15	6.73 ^c ±0.15	7.80 ^d ±0.10
Control soil	3.50 ^a ±0.10	5.10 ^a ±0.10	6.80 ^a ±0.10	8.10 ^{ab} ±0.10	9.60 ^a ±0.10

* Mean with different superscripts within the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$); Bacterial Isolates - A1D3E1Z2

Table 6: Leaf Area (cm²) of Maize Plants as influenced by Bacteria Isolates under Bitumen Contaminated Soil

Treatments	Number of Weeks				
	2	4	6	8	10
Contaminated soil + Bacteria Isolates	13.73 ^d ±0.68	39.10 ^c ±1.25	99.90 ^d ±2.80	181.71 ^c ±2.39	255.90 ^c ±3.28
Contaminated soil + Bacterial Isolates + Biostimulant	16.41 ^c ±0.62	43.77 ^b ±2.12	115.53 ^b ±0.80	197.03 ^a ±4.25	286.47 ^b ±3.54
Contaminated soil + Biostimulant	22.94 ^a ±0.95	48.25 ^b ±0.40	110.93 ^c ±2.11	189.11 ^b ±4.13	293.02 ^b ±5.04
Contaminated soil	20.14 ^b ±0.44	38.62 ^c ±1.22	97.98 ^d ±1.94	178.28 ^c ±4.89	256.24 ^c ±4.46
Control soil	16.71 ^c ±0.52	47.31 ^a ±1.38	126.83 ^a ±2.40	201.28 ^a ±2.01	307.20 ^a ±2.52

* Mean with different superscripts within the same column are significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$); Bacterial Isolates-A1D3E1

The plant shoot from the contaminated soil without any other treatment had a TPH concentration of 3.30±0.01 mg/kg, which was the highest concentration in the shoot. This indicates that the hydrocarbon accumulation in the shoot was also influenced by the presence of microorganisms.

However, the addition of a biostimulant to the microorganisms did not seem to significantly affect the hydrocarbon concentration in the shoot. Overall, the introduction of bacterial isolates degraded the TPH and probably obstructed its uptake into plant tissues. The percentage of the TPH concentration in the soil and plant root as well as shoot of the contaminated soils were 22.21%, 6.25% and 4.83% respectively, however, significant reduction (17.77%, 0.51% and 0.13%) were observed with the addition of microorganisms to the treatment for both the soil and plant tissues.

Petroleum in soil is toxic to plants and could inhibit the germination of seeds. Various researchers have reported forms of hydrocarbons subdue seed germination (Eriyamremu *et al.*, 1999; Anoliefo and Edegbai, 2000; Njoku *et al.*, 2008). It has been reported that hydrocarbons induced metabolic modifications in plants (Achuba, 2006; Peretiemo-Clarke and Achuba, 2007; Achuba and Okoh, 2015), including increased production of organic macromolecules in plants (Achuba, 2006). However, the maize seeds sown in all the treatments for this study germinated, though their growth rate differed. This could be as a result of a lower concentration used in spiking the soil used for sowing. Agbogidi and Eshegbeyi (2006) reported there could be toxic aftermath on the germination potential of seeds as the concentration of hydrocarbon increases. The presence of microorganisms (consortium) and or fish pond effluent (biostimulant) would also have imparted the germination rate of the respective treatments.

Roots play a crucial role in absorbing hydrocarbons from contaminated soil, however, the presence of microorganisms and or biostimulant further reduced the hydrocarbon uptake. This agreed with the findings of various researchers on the ability of roots to uptake petroleum hydrocarbon from the environment (Chen *et al.*, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2019; Wei *et al.*, 2021; Grifoni *et al.*, 2020). The presence of microorganisms influenced the hydrocarbon accumulation, lowering it, as observed in the plant root from contaminated soil + with microorganisms. The ability of microorganisms to remediate petroleum hydrocarbon in soil agreed with other authors (Xun *et al.*, 2015; Hoang *et al.*, 2021; Zuzolo *et al.*, 2021; Kudakwashe *et al.*, 2022). Shoots accumulate lower hydrocarbon concentrations, and there was no significant difference upon the addition of a biostimulant.

Table 7: Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon Content of Soil and Tissues of Maize after Harvesting

Initial Concentration of Bitumen Contaminated Soil (mg/kg)	Parameter	TPH (mg/kg)		
		Soil	Root	Shoot
68.31±0.02	CS	15.17 ^a ±0.00	4.27 ^a ±0.04	3.30 ^a ±0.01
	CSB	12.14 ^c ±0.01	0.35 ^d ±0.00	0.09 ^c ±0.01
	CSOE	10.28 ^d ±0.04	0.58 ^c ±0.01	0.08 ^c ±0.00
	CSE	13.92 ^b ±0.02	3.21 ^b ±0.01	2.54 ^b ±0.01

* Mean with different superscripts within the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$); Bacterial Isolates - A1D3E1Z2

CS – Contaminated Soil

CSB - Contaminated Soil + Bacterial Isolates,

CSE - Contaminated Soil + Biostimulant

CSBE - Contaminated Soil + Bacterial Isolates + Biostimulant,

BCS - Bitumen Contaminated Soil

The highest growth rate pattern was observed in the treatment with contaminated soil + fish pond waste treatment while the least was in contaminated soil + microorganisms. This phenomenon could be due to microorganisms initially breaking down the complex compounds present in the bitumen hydrocarbon contaminant thereby making nutrients in the soil unavailable for the plant's uptake. This agreed with the work of Onuorah *et al.* (2021) who observed that maize plants grown on amended soils did better than on unamended soils. The difference in growth rate observed could be attributed to disruption in the soil structure by the presence of the hydrocarbon and in turn disruption in the nutrient uptake by the maize (Murakami *et al.*, 2008; Njoku *et al.*, 2008; Jain *et al.*, 2011). Dimitrow and Markow (2000) reported that hydrocarbons decrease the availability of phosphorous and potassium in the soil to plant. These nutrients are essential for plant growth and development; hence reduction in the bioavailability will lead to reduced plant growth (Njoku *et al.*, 2008). Also, the reduction in maize growth could be attributed to the inhibition or reduction in cell expansions and other biochemical processes (Athar, *et al.*, 2016; Kudoyarova *et al.*, 2019).

Ali *et al.* (2021) reported a reduction in the phytotoxic effects of petroleum hydrocarbons on maize growth in the presence of Bacillus strain MN54 and biochar, this showed the importance of microbes and biochar addition on plant growth in a contaminated soil (Hussain *et al.*, 2019). This did not agree with the findings of this study as untreated contaminated soil and contaminated soil with biostimulant had better growth rate. It has been reported that microbes due to their plant growth promoting characteristics (such as P solubilization, ACC-deaminase activity and siderophore formation) enhance plant growth even under pollutant stress or toxic environment (Iqbal *et al.*, 2019; Rajput *et al.*, 2021). According to Peretiemo-Clarke and Achuba (2007), hydrocarbon (petroleum and its products) could affect plants during growth at different physiological stages which culminate in reduction in yield through its effects on morphological indices. This did not agree with the findings of this study as increased growth rate was observed in untreated bitumen contaminated soil and contaminated soil with biostimulants. This has implications of high risk of bioaccumulation which could probably enter the food chain resulting in biomagnification with severe health issues in man and animals (Wang *et al.*, 2021). According to Tang *et al.* (2010), the safety of the ecosystem and human health can be directly affected by the accumulation of hydrocarbons in the environment. Some of the aftermaths of this include inhibition of plant growth and destruction of soil structure amongst others (Besalatpour *et al.*, 2008; Murakami *et al.* 2008; Jain *et al.* 2011).

The results of this study established the high tolerance of maize in hydrocarbon-polluted soils. This agreed with the work of Ayotamuno and Kogbara (2007) that *Zea mays* has a high tolerance level compared to many other crops and could be

grown on soils with contaminant concentration of about 21% by volume of the soil. However, the effect of the bioaccumulation and biomagnification of this contaminant on the environment was not put into consideration.

From this study, it was observed that the addition of microorganisms and fish pond waste (as biostimulant) had positive effect on the maize grown in bitumen contaminated soil. The addition of microorganisms and fish pond waste not only enhanced the growth of the maize but reduced the toxicity and relieved the inhibitory effect of the hydrocarbon present in the soil, making the plants thrives better. This agreed with the study of Eluehike *et al.* (2019), where they reported that the addition sawdust inhibited the effect of crude oil on the growth of plant.

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